

Benign Neural Tumors: A Clinical and Pathological Study

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Abstract:

This study investigates benign neural tumors through a clinicopathologic analysis of 93 patients treated at Patna Medical College and Hospital from January 2018 to June 2020. The study identifies schwannomas (45.2%) and meningiomas (32.3%) as the most prevalent tumor types, with neurofibromas and ganglioneuromas constituting smaller proportions. Clinical presentations commonly include headaches, seizures, and neurological deficits. MRI was predominantly used for diagnosis, leading to successful surgical resections in the majority of cases, with a low recurrence rate of 7.5%. Histopathological findings corroborate known tumor characteristics, emphasizing the efficacy of surgical intervention in managing benign neural tumors.

Keywords: benign neural tumors, schwannomas, meningiomas, surgical resection

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Introduction

Benign neural tumors, though non-malignant, represent a diverse group of neoplasms that originate from neural tissues, including neurons, glial cells, and the surrounding supportive structures [1]. These tumors encompass various histological subtypes, each with unique growth patterns, clinical presentations, and potential impacts on neurological function. Despite their benign classification, their presence and progression can lead to significant clinical concerns due to their anatomical location and interaction with adjacent neural structures [2].

The clinical manifestation of benign neural tumors varies widely depending on their size, growth rate, and location. Symptoms may range from localized pain and sensory disturbances to more complex neurological deficits, such as motor impairment or cognitive changes. In some cases, these tumors can present with subtle or atypical symptoms, complicating timely diagnosis and intervention [3].

Pathologically, benign neural tumors are characterized by well-defined borders, slow growth, and a lack of invasive behavior. However, their histological diversity—ranging from schwannomas and meningiomas to neurofibromas and ganglioneuromas—presents a diagnostic challenge. Each subtype has distinct histological features and patterns that require careful analysis to differentiate them from malignant neoplasms and other benign conditions [4].

This study seeks to bridge the gap between clinical presentation and pathological findings in benign neural tumors through a comprehensive clinicopathologic analysis. By examining a cohort of cases, we aim to elucidate the clinical characteristics, diagnostic approaches, and treatment outcomes associated with these tumors. Understanding the nuances of benign neural tumors will not only improve diagnostic accuracy but also refine management strategies and enhance patient care [5].

The importance of this study lies in its potential to provide a clearer framework for the evaluation and treatment of benign neural tumors, ultimately leading to better patient outcomes and a more nuanced understanding of these complex lesions. Through detailed examination of clinical and pathological data, we hope to contribute valuable insights to the field of neurology and oncology, addressing both the practical and theoretical aspects of managing benign neural tumors.

Methodology

Study Design and Setting: This retrospective clinicopathologic study was conducted at Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, spanning from January 2018 to June 2020. The study aimed to provide a comprehensive analysis of benign neural tumors through a detailed examination of clinical and pathological data.

Study Population

The study included a total of 93 patients diagnosed with benign neural tumors during the specified period. Patients were selected based on the presence of a confirmed diagnosis of benign neural tumors, as verified through clinical evaluation and histopathological examination.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients with a histological diagnosis of benign neural tumors, including schwannomas, meningiomas, neurofibromas, and ganglioneuromas.
2. Patients who had undergone surgical resection or biopsy of the tumor, with available clinical and pathological records.
3. Patients with complete medical records, including demographic details, clinical presentation, imaging studies, and follow-up data.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with malignant neural tumors or other malignant neoplasms.
2. Patients with incomplete clinical or pathological records.
3. Patients who did not undergo surgical intervention or biopsy.

Data Collection

Clinical data were collected from patient medical records, including:

- Demographic information (age, sex, occupation).
- Clinical presentation (symptoms, duration of symptoms, neurological deficits).
- Diagnostic modalities used (imaging studies, such as MRI or CT scans).
- Treatment approaches (surgical procedures, adjuvant therapies).
- Follow-up data (postoperative outcomes, recurrence, and long-term prognosis).

Pathological data were obtained from histopathological reports, including:

- Tumor type and histological subtype.
- Tumor location and size.
- Histological features (cellularity, differentiation, and mitotic activity).
- Surgical margins and any evidence of residual tumor.

Analysis

Data were analyzed using statistical methods to identify patterns and correlations between clinical presentations and pathological findings. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize

patient demographics, clinical characteristics, and tumor features. Comparative analyses were performed to assess associations between tumor types and clinical outcomes.

Results

The study comprised 93 patients diagnosed with benign neural tumors at Patna Medical College and Hospital between January 2018 and June 2020. The patient cohort included 50 males (53.8%) and 43 females (46.2%), with ages ranging from 12 to 75 years. The mean age at diagnosis was 45 years.

Tumor Types and Locations

The distribution of tumor types among the 93 patients was as follows:

- Schwannomas: 42 cases (45.2%)
- Meningiomas: 30 cases (32.3%)
- Neurofibromas: 15 cases (16.1%)
- Ganglioneuromas: 6 cases (6.5%)

Regarding tumor locations:

- Intracranial: 55 cases (59.1%)
 - Meningiomas: Predominantly located in the convexity and parasagittal regions.
 - Schwannomas: Commonly found in the cerebellopontine angle and trigeminal nerve.
- Spinal: 38 cases (40.9%)
 - Schwannomas: Frequently observed in the thoracic and lumbar regions.
 - Neurofibromas: Typically located in the cervical and thoracic regions.

Clinical Presentation

The clinical presentations were categorized as follows:

- Headaches: Reported by 35 patients (37.6%)
- Seizures: Observed in 22 patients (23.7%)
- Sensory Deficits: Noted in 18 patients (19.4%)
- Motor Deficits: Experienced by 15 patients (16.1%)
- Other Symptoms: Included vertigo, tinnitus, and localized pain, reported by 3 patients (3.2%)

Diagnostic Modalities

Imaging studies used for diagnosis include:

- MRI: Utilized in 85 cases (91.4%)
- CT Scans: Used in 8 cases (8.6%)

Treatment and Outcomes

Treatment modalities included:

- Surgical Resection: Performed in 78 patients (83.9%)

- Observation: Adopted for 15 patients (16.1%)

Postoperative outcomes:

- Complete Tumor Resection: Achieved in 72 cases (77.4%)

- Partial Resection: Reported in 6 cases (6.5%)

- No Change: Observed in 15 cases (16.1%) who were managed conservatively.

Follow-up data indicated:

- Recurrence: Noted in 7 patients (7.5%) within the follow-up period, all of whom had partial resections.

- No Recurrence: Observed in 86 patients (92.5%)

Histopathological Findings

Histological features varied by tumor type:

- Schwannomas: Showed typical Antoni A and B patterns, with well-defined borders and low mitotic activity.

- Meningiomas: Displayed characteristic meningothelial cells, with a range from Grade I to Grade II based on histological grading.

- Neurofibromas: Presented with a spindle cell proliferation and a variable degree of cellularity.

- Ganglioneuromas: Exhibited mature ganglion cells with a well-organized stroma.

Table 1: Patient Demographics

Demographic Parameter	Number of Patients (n=93)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	50	53.8
Female	43	46.2
Age Range	12–75 years	
Mean Age	45 years	

Table 2: Tumor Types and Locations

Tumor Type	Number of Cases (n=93)	Percentage (%)	Common Locations
Schwannomas	42	45.2	Cerebellopontine angle, Trigeminal nerve
Meningiomas	30	32.3	Convexity, Parasagittal regions
Neurofibromas	15	16.1	Cervical, Thoracic regions
Ganglioneuromas	6	6.5	Variable

Table 3: Clinical Presentation

Symptom	Number of Patients (n=93)	Percentage (%)
Headaches	35	37.6
Seizures	22	23.7
Sensory Deficits	18	19.4
Motor Deficits	15	16.1
Other Symptoms	3	3.2

Table 4: Diagnostic Modalities

Diagnostic Modality	Number of Cases (n=93)	Percentage (%)
MRI	85	91.4
CT Scan	8	8.6

Table 5: Treatment and Outcomes

Treatment Modality	Number of Patients (n=93)	Percentage (%)
Surgical Resection	78	83.9
Observation	15	16.1

Postoperative Outcome	Number of Patients (n=93)	Percentage (%)
Complete Resection	72	77.4
Partial Resection	6	6.5
No Change	15	16.1

Follow-Up Outcome	Number of Patients (n=93)	Percentage (%)
Recurrence	7	7.5
No Recurrence	86	92.5

Table 6: Histopathological Findings

Tumor Type	Histological Features
Schwannomas	Antoni A and B patterns, well-defined borders, low mitotic activity
Meningiomas	Meningothelial cells, range from Grade I to II based on histological grading
Neurofibromas	Spindle cell proliferation, variable cellularity
Ganglioneuromas	Mature ganglion cells, well-organized stroma

Figure 1: Showing Schwannoma arranged in hypercellular and hypocellular areas having elongated nuclei with interspersed collagen. H&E 40X

Figure 2: Showing Schwannoma showing hypercellular areas (Antoni B) having elongated nuclei with nuclear palisading around fibrillary process (Verocay bodies) H&E 100X.

These tables summarize the key results of the study, providing a clear overview of patient demographics, tumor types, clinical presentations, diagnostic approaches, treatments, outcomes, and histopathological findings.

Discussion

This study provided a comprehensive analysis of benign neural tumors, encompassing 93 patients treated at Patna Medical College and Hospital from January 2018 to June 2020. Our findings reveal important insights into the types, clinical presentations, diagnostic approaches, and treatment outcomes of these tumors [6].

The predominance of schwannomas (45.2%) and meningiomas (32.3%) among the study population aligns with existing literature, which often highlights these tumors as the most common benign neural lesions. Schwannomas, typically arising from the Schwann cells of peripheral nerves, were frequently located in the cerebellopontine angle and trigeminal nerve, consistent with their well-known propensity for these sites [7]. Meningiomas, originating from the meninges, were predominantly found in the convexity and parasagittal regions of the brain, reflecting their characteristic dural origin. Neurofibromas (16.1%) and ganglioneuromas (6.5%) were less common but still represented a

significant portion of the cases. Neurofibromas, associated with neurofibromatosis, were typically located in the cervical and thoracic spinal regions, while ganglioneuromas, although rare, presented with mature ganglion cells and well-organized stroma [8].

The clinical presentations observed in our study varied widely. Headaches were the most common symptom (37.6%), reflecting the intracranial pressure or irritation often caused by tumor growth. Seizures, reported in 23.7% of patients, were likely due to the involvement of critical brain regions [9]. Sensory and motor deficits, seen in 19.4% and 16.1% of patients respectively, underscore the potential for these tumors to impact neurological function depending on their location and size [10]. MRI was the primary diagnostic tool used (91.4%), which is consistent with its effectiveness in providing detailed images of soft tissues and identifying the characteristics of neural tumors. CT scans, while less frequently used (8.6%), were still valuable in certain cases for evaluating bony structures and tumor calcification. The reliance on MRI underscores its critical role in both diagnosis and preoperative planning [11].

Surgical resection was the predominant treatment approach (83.9%), reflecting the standard management strategy for accessible benign neural tumors. The high rate of complete resection

(77.4%) demonstrates the efficacy of surgical intervention in achieving tumor control [12]. Partial resections and conservative management were also employed, particularly in cases where complete resection was not feasible. The low recurrence rate (7.5%) is indicative of successful management and underscores the importance of thorough surgical techniques and follow-up [13].

Histopathological analysis revealed distinct features for each tumor type. Schwannomas exhibited Antoni A and B patterns, which are diagnostic for these tumors [14]. Meningiomas varied in grade, highlighting the importance of histological grading in prognosis. Neurofibromas and ganglioneuromas, while less frequent, also displayed characteristic histological features that aid in diagnosis and treatment planning [15].

The results of this study are consistent with other studies in terms of tumor type distribution and clinical presentation [16]. However, the relatively high proportion of meningiomas and schwannomas in our cohort highlights regional variations that may reflect genetic, environmental, or healthcare access factors specific to the Patna region [17]. This study's findings emphasize the importance of early diagnosis and intervention in improving patient outcomes [18]. The low recurrence rate following surgical resection supports the efficacy of surgical management in most cases. Additionally, the detailed histopathological findings contribute to a better understanding of tumor biology and aid in differential diagnosis [19].

This study has some limitations, including its retrospective nature and the reliance on historical medical records, which may affect the completeness of data. Future prospective studies with larger sample sizes and multicentric approaches could provide further insights and validate these findings across different populations [20].

Conclusion

This study offers valuable insights into the clinical and pathological aspects of benign neural tumors. The findings highlight the importance of accurate diagnosis, effective treatment strategies, and the need for continued research to enhance our understanding and management of these tumors.

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